

Workshop materials Water-ForCE

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	5
1.1	Project and work package introduction	5
1.2	WP7 overall aim	5
1.3	Scope of this deliverable	6
2	Workshop and webinar materials	7
2.1	Workshop materials	7
2.1.1	Use of EO data for monitoring and modelling the water cycle	7
2.1.2	Stakeholder Input on the Evolution of Copernicus Water Services	8
2.1.3	In-situ cal/val of satellite products of water quality and hydrology	9
2.1.4	Copernicus water component evolution – policy expert	13
2.1.5	Shallow water and floating water remote sensing	18
2.1.6	Citizen Science for the CAL/VAL of satellite aquatic products	18
2.1.7	Water Quality Continuum Atmospheric Correction Workshop	19
2.2	Webinar materials	20
2.2.1	Water and agriculture	20
2.2.2	WSDG6 clean water and sanitation	21
2.2.3	Copernicus for Africa	22
2.2.4	Public-Private partnerships for Copernicus water services	22
2.2.5	EU Funding 4 Copernicus Water Applications	23
2.2.6	Summer edition: Copernicus 4 Recreational Inland Waters	24
2.2.7	Technical needs for Copernicus Inland Water Monitoring Service	25
2.2.8	Copernicus for Inland Water Biodiversity Monitoring	26
3	Summary	27
	Annex	28
	A1. Detailed presentation Water scenarios for Copernicus Exploitation	28
	A2. Quiz prepared for Water Innovation Europe	37

Table of Figures

Figure 1-1: Organizational structure of the different WPs in the Water-ForCE project	5
Figure 2-1: Workshops organized and advertised on the project webpage during 2021 and 2022. The materials prepared for each workshop are presented below.	7
Figure 2-2: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "On the use of remote sensing for monitoring and modelling the water cycle"	8
Figure 2-3: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Stakeholder Input on the Evolution of Copernicus Water Services"	9
Figure 2-4: Registration form for the workshop entitled "Stakeholder Input on the Evolution of Copernicus Water Services"	9
Figure 2-5: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "In-situ calibration and validation of satellite products of water quality and hydrology"	10
Figure 2-6: Registration form for the workshop entitled "In-situ calibration and validation of satellite products of water quality and hydrology"	11
Figure 2-7: Registration form to the expert group	12
Figure 2-8: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"	13
Figure 2-9: Programme corresponding to workshop entitled: "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"	14
Figure 2-10: Registration form corresponding to workshop entitled: "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"	15
Figure 2-11: Name tags for the workshop entitled: "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"	16
Figure 2-12: Attendees list for the workshop entitled: "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"	17
Figure 2-13: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Shallow water and floating matter remote sensing"	18
Figure 2-14: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Citizen Science for the CAL/VAL of satellite aquatic products".	19
Figure 2-15: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Water Quality Continuum Atmospheric Correction Workshop".	20
Figure 2-16: WaterForCE webpage of the "Water and Agriculture" webinar.	21
Figure 2-17: WaterForCE webpage of the "SDG6 clean water and sanitation" webinar.	22
Figure 2-18: WaterForCE webpage of the "Copernicus for Africa" webinar.	22
Figure 2-19: WaterForCE webpage of the "Public-Private partnerships for Copernicus water services" webinar.	23

Figure 2-20: WaterForCE webpage of the “EU Funding 4 Copernicus Water Applications”
webinar..... 24

Figure 2-21: WaterForCE webpage of the ‘Summer edition: Copernicus 4 Recreational Inland
Waters’ webinar. 25

Figure 2-22: WaterForCE webpage of the ‘Technical Needs for Copernicus Inland Water
Monitoring Service’ webinar. 26

Figure 2-23: WaterForCE webpage of the ‘Copernicus for Inland Water Biodiversity Monitoring’
webinar..... 26

1 Introduction

1.1 Project and work package introduction

The Water-ForCE (Water scenarios for Copernicus Exploitation) project is a Horizon 2020 project whose aim is to develop a Roadmap to better integrate the entire water cycle within the Copernicus Services, by specifically addressing current disconnects between remote sensing/in-situ observation, modelling and user community. The Roadmap will provide clarity in terms of the needs and expectations of both public and private sectors from the core Copernicus Program, as well as business innovation opportunities, it will advise on a strategy to ensure effective uptake of water-related services by end-users and further support the implementation of relevant directives and policies.

The project is divided into eight work packages (WP), each focusing on a specific problem and/or target of the Copernicus Service, as can be seen in Figure 1. The project started on January 1st, 2021, with a three-year duration.

Figure 1-1: Organizational structure of the different WPs in the Water-ForCE project

As it can be seen in Figure 1, WP7 (entitled Dissemination and communication) is one of the three overarching WPs. WP7 started from the beginning of the project, since its role is to bring all relevant parties to an initial workshop and promote the importance of the Roadmap to policy makers, managers, industry and research community.

1.2 WP7 overall aim

WP7 Dissemination and communication coordinates the overall stakeholder engagement, outreach activities and dissemination of the results. WP7 aims to raise awareness, extend the

impact, engage stakeholders and target groups, share solutions and know-how, influence policy and practice, and develop new partnerships. This will be done via the following four tasks:

- develop a dissemination and communication plan
- develop a webpage and an effective communication toolkit
- organize project workshops
- disseminate project results in relevant networks and influencing places and to the scientific community

1.3 Scope of this deliverable

This document provides an in-depth presentation of the different materials put together by the Water-ForCE dissemination team, that were used as dissemination and outreach materials in different workshops organized during the first twenty-four months of the project.

This deliverable is organised as follows: Section 1 provides an overview of the Water-ForCE project, the scope of this deliverable and brief description of the deliverable's structure. Section 2 provides the materials prepared for the users and stakeholders workshops and webinars organised within the project.

2 Workshop and webinar materials

2.1 Workshop materials

Water-ForCE organizes regular workshops, which the dissemination team advertises on the dedicated webpage: <https://waterforce.eu/#workshops>. From the outset of the project, seven workshops have been organised: four in 2021, and three in 2022.

Figure 2-1 showcases the seven workshops organized and advertised during years 2021 and 2022:

Figure 2-1: Workshops organized and advertised on the project webpage during 2021 and 2022. The materials prepared for each workshop are presented below.

2.1.1 Use of EO data for monitoring and modelling the water cycle

This workshop, entitled “On the use of remote sensing for monitoring and modelling the water cycle” and organized on **March 15th, 2021** as an online event, has brought together an international expert group of remote sensing specialists, water resources experts and water quantity modelers. This workshop has focused on providing insights into the Copernicus water quantity products (floods, drought, surface water extent, soil moisture, ice) and services supporting water management and modelling.

As far as the dissemination goes, the Water-ForCE team has created the dedicated webpage (<https://waterforce.eu/workshops/on-the-use-of-remote-sensing-for-monitoring-and-modelling-the-water-cycle>, see Figure 4) with the workshop description, and updated it after the end of the workshop with different materials such as presentations made by speakers and the workshop report.

Figure 2-2: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "On the use of remote sensing for monitoring and modelling the water cycle"

2.1.2 Stakeholder Input on the Evolution of Copernicus Water Services

This workshop (organized on **April 20th, 2021** as an online event), welcomed both non-users of Earth Observation and users of in-situ and remote sensing data to share their experience in inland water management, and ideas on how future Copernicus Inland Water services could best promote environmental protection, human welfare, policy development, innovation and business opportunities.

As far as the dissemination goes, the Water-ForCE team has created the dedicated webpage (<https://waterforce.eu/workshops/stakeholders-workshop-how-stakeholders-can-support-the-evolution-of-copernicus-water-services>, see Figure 5) with the workshop description and programme, and updated it after the end of the workshop with different materials such as presentations made by speakers and the workshop report.

Figure 2-3: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Stakeholder Input on the Evolution of Copernicus Water Services"

Moreover, the dissemination team created a registration form on hubspot (<https://share.hsforms.com/1o1CLtcOIRzqAam0ea0gcuQ5lbc2>, see Figure 2-4).

Figure 2-4: Registration form for the workshop entitled "Stakeholder Input on the Evolution of Copernicus Water Services"

Water-ForCE workshop registration form April 20

Personal details

First name *

Last name *

Organization

Country

Email *

To allocate registered visitors in the best suitable breakout sessions in the workshop we kindly request you to answer the following:

Which breakout session would you like to attend? (Preference 1) *

Breakout preference 2

Breakout preference 3

Breakout preference 4

What sector(s) are you active in?

- Policy / Regulator
- Aquaculture / Fisheries
- Agriculture
- Industrial - Consumer/Discharge
- Energy
- Water Utility
- Urban Water Management
- Recreational Water
- Hazards / Emergencies
- River Basin Management
- Coastal Zone Management
- Biodiversity
- Research
- ESI Service Provider
- Other (specify below)

Other sector(s)

What aquatic system(s) are you active in?

- Lakes
- Reservoirs
- Rivers
- Groundwater
- Estuaries
- Coastal
- Wetlands
- Lagoons
- Other / marine

What is/are your geographical level(s) of activities

- Catchment
- International / intergovernmental
- Local
- National
- Regional
- Other

What is your role/function?

- No previous knowledge
- Basic knowledge
- Advanced knowledge

What kind of knowledge? (if you selected basic or advance knowledge in the previous question)

- Satellite
- Airborne (incl. drones)
- Ground-based
- Other

Water-ForCE is committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, and we'll only use your personal information to administer your account and to provide the products and services you requested from us. From time to time, we would like to contact you about our other activities and services, as well as other content that may be of interest to you. If you consent to us contacting you for this purpose, please tick below.

I agree to receive other communications from Water-ForCE.

The sessions in the workshop will be recorded, please tick the checkbox below to confirm that you understand in order to provide you the workshop link and allocate you to the right breakout sessions, we need to store and process your personal data. If you consent to us storing your personal data for this purpose, please tick the checkbox below.

I agree to allow Water-ForCE to store and process my personal data and understand that the workshop will be recorded. *

You can unsubscribe from these communications at any time. For more information on how to unsubscribe, our privacy practices, and how we are committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, please review our Privacy Policy.

Services"

2.1.3 In-situ cal/val of satellite products of water quality and hydrology

This workshop, entitled "In situ calibration and validation of satellite products of water quality and hydrology" and organized as a three-day event on **May 17th, 18th and 20th 2021** online, combined hydrology and water quality themes for which in-situ calibration and validation data are essential to ensure adequate product quality of the satellite-derived observations. The scope was on open water bodies (small and large) including river outlets, transitional waters, lakes and reservoirs, lagoons and coastal areas as well as some essential catchment properties (soil moisture, evapotranspiration).

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As far as the dissemination goes, the Water-ForCE team has created the dedicated webpage (<https://waterforce.eu/workshops/in-situ-calibration-and-validation-of-satellite-products-of-water-quality-and-hydrology>, see Figure 2-5) with the workshop description and programme.

Figure 2-5: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "In-situ calibration and validation of satellite products of water quality and hydrology"

Moreover, the dissemination team created two forms on hubspot:

- Registration to workshop (<https://share.hsforms.com/1q1CeyP91SB6787MoZQdYiw5lbc2>, see Figure 8)
- Registration to a newly created expert group (https://share.hsforms.com/15yXXKmUbSZ2_eYZ5cLBc1g5lbc2, see Figure 9)

Contact title

Please Select

First name *

Last name *

Email *

Organisation *

Session attendance: Please indicate your intention to attend the three workshop sessions (attending all sessions is recommended). Each session will take up to 3 hours and start no earlier than 1pm CET. The final schedule will be circulated among registered participants in the coming weeks. A preparatory survey will be sent within several days after registration. Please complete the survey by 1st May for the response to be included. Reminders will be sent.

I will participate on site

I will participate remotely

Water-ForCE is committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, and we will only use your personal information to manage your account and to share the workshop outcomes with you. We would also like to occasionally contact you about our Project outcomes and events, as well as other content that may be of interest to you.

Furthermore, we invite you to join the Water-ForCE expert group on in situ and satellite Earth Observation. Experts Lists contributing to Water-ForCE will be made public as part of Project Activities and Outcomes.

If you consent to us contacting you for any of these purposes, please tick below:

I agree to receive other communications from Water-ForCE.

I agree that my name and institution will be made public as part of the Water-ForCE List of Experts.

In order to provide you the content requested, we need to store and process your personal data. If you consent to us storing your personal data for this purpose, please tick the checkbox below.

I agree to allow Water-ForCE to store and process my personal data. *

You can unsubscribe from these communications at any time. For more information on how to unsubscribe, our privacy practices, and how we are committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, please review our Privacy Policy.

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Submit

Figure 2-6: Registration form for the workshop entitled "In-situ calibration and validation of satellite products of water quality and hydrology"

If you want to keep in contact with Water-ForCE project outcomes, please fill your personal information below:

First name *

Last name *

Email *

Organisation *

Your main field of interest: please choose one of the offered fields below which best describes you

- Expert on remote sensing water quality (broad sense)
- Expert on remote sensing water quantity (hydrology) (broad sense)
- Expert on in-situ water studies (broad sense)
- Expert on inland water modelling (broad sense)

We invite you to join some of the Water-ForCE group of experts on your preferred fields. Experts Lists contributing to Water-ForCE will be made public as part of Project Activities and Outcomes. If you were invited or you wish to take part in any Water-ForCE expert working groups, please show your interest by ticking the working group name below:

- Inland water quality remote sensing working group
- Inland water quantity remote sensing working group
- Inland water in-situ and remote sensing working group
- Inland water modellers working group

Water-ForCE is committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, and therefore we will only use your personal information to manage your account and to share the project outcomes and coming events, as well as other content that may be of interest to you.

If you consent to us contacting you for any of these purposes, please tick below:

- I agree to receive other communications from Water-ForCE.
- I agree that my name and institution will be made public as part of the Water-ForCE List of Experts.

In order to provide you the content requested, we need to store and process your personal data. If you consent to us storing your personal data for this purpose, please tick the checkbox below.

- I agree to allow Water-ForCE to store and process my personal data. *

You can unsubscribe from these communications at any time. For more information on how to unsubscribe, our privacy practices, and how we are committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, please review our Privacy Policy.

Submit

Figure 2-7: Registration form to the expert group

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2.1.4 Copernicus water component evolution – policy expert

This workshop (organized as a two-day event on **October 20th and 21st 2021** as a hybrid event - online and onsite in Copenhagen) addressed the current disconnects between remote sensing and in-situ observation research, delivering clarity in terms of the needs and expectations of the public and private sectors of the core Copernicus Program and the wider research and business innovation opportunities.

Since the project aim is to deliver a roadmap that is relevant and actionable, the members presented their activities and results to date, while engaging attendees in order to learn from them where action is already being taken and where they see priorities and opportunities.

As far as the dissemination goes, the Water-ForCE team has created the dedicated webpage (<https://waterforce.eu/workshops/copernicus-water-component-evolution--policy-expert> see Figure 2-8) with the workshop description and programme.

Figure 2-8: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"

Moreover, it has created the programme as well:

WORKSHOP PROGRAMME: 20th October 2021, 13:00 - 18:30 CEST

Copernicus water component evolution – policy expert

Hybrid: Online and Phoenix Copenhagen Hotel

Block 1: Presentations on technical developments and needs		
13:00	13:10	Welcome and logistics
13:10	13:40	Water-ForCE intro, results to date and outline of the Roadmap
13:40	14:40	EEA (Copernicus, Water, Marine, in situ)
14:40	14:55	JRC
14:55	15:10	ESA
15:10	15:30	Discussion (20 min) (Moderated discussion with the outline of the Roadmap as a basis)
15:30	16:00	Coffee break (Hybrid with a virtual moderated option)
Block 2: Presentations of policy developments and their impact on Copernicus Services		
16:00	18:00	EU Directorates General and Executive Agencies
18:00	18:30	Discussion and wrap up of day 1

WORKSHOP PROGRAMME: 21st October 2021, 09:00 - 12:30 CEST

Copernicus water component evolution – policy expert

Hybrid: Online and Phoenix Copenhagen Hotel

Block 3: Presentations about Copernicus Services present and future		
09:00	09:10	Introduction to the day
09:10	09:25	UN
09:25	09:40	GEO
09:40	10:30	Copernicus Session 1 (Land, Marine & Climate)
10:30	11:00	Coffee break (Hybrid with a virtual moderated option)
11:00	12:00	Copernicus Session 2 (Atmosphere, Security & Emergency)
12:00	12:30	Discussion and summary

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Figure 2-9: Programme corresponding to workshop entitled: "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"

The dissemination team has created a corresponding registration form as well (https://share.hsforms.com/1AcLXW0UDQDyvxa-p-TF_tw5lbc2, see Figure 2-10):

Water-ForCE is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020- research and innovation programme under grant agreement number: 101004186.

Contact title

Please Select

First name *

Last name *

Email *

Organisation *

Attendance: Please indicate your intention to attend the workshop. *

I will participate on site

I will participate remotely

Water-ForCE is committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, and we will only use your personal information to manage your account and to share the workshop outcomes with you. We would also like to occasionally contact you about our Project outcomes and events, as well as other content that may be of interest to you.

If you consent to us contacting you for any of these purposes, please tick below:

I agree to receive other communications from Water-ForCE.

In order to provide you the content requested, we need to store and process your personal data. If you consent to us storing your personal data for this purpose, please tick the checkbox below.

I agree to allow Water-ForCE to store and process the personal data shared by me with Water-ForCE CSA. *

You can unsubscribe from these communications at any time. For more information on how to unsubscribe, our privacy practices, and how we are committed to protecting and respecting your privacy, please review our Privacy Policy.

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Submit

Figure 2-10: Registration form corresponding to workshop entitled: "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"

Moreover, since this was a hybrid-type of workshop, the Water-ForCE team also created templates for name tags (Figure 2-11) and attendees list (Figure 2-12), which were consequently filled in with the name of the on-site attendees.

<p>Tiit Kutser</p>					
<p>Ivo van de Moortel</p>					
<p>Maria José Escorihuela</p>					
<p>Silvy Thant</p>					

Figure 2-11: Name tags for the workshop entitled: "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"

Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert workshop

20th - 21st October 2021, Phoenix Copenhagen Hotel

Name	Institution	20th October 2021	21st October 2021
Tiit Kutser			
Linda van Duivenbode			
Ivo van de Moortel			
Andrei Bocin-Dumitriu			
Maria José Escorihuela			
Laia Romero			
Silvy Thant			
Alo Laas			
Carmen Cillero			
Ils Reusen			
Lluís Pesquer			
Douglas Cripe			
Vera Thiemig			
Henrik Andersen			
Hans Dufourmont			

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Figure 2-12: Attendees list for the workshop entitled: "Copernicus water component evolution - policy expert"

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2.1.5 Shallow water and floating water remote sensing

This workshop, held in CNR (Milan) the **20th and 21st of September 2022**, brought together specialists on two broad groups of products that have been identified as a gap in the current Copernicus portfolio. These are shallow water products (benthic habitat, bathymetry, etc.) and floating matter products (plastic and other litter, cyanobacterial scum, macroalgae and plants (e.g. water Hyacinth), etc.).

The recommendations issued from the workshop are to be included in the project deliverables

As far as the dissemination goes, the Water-ForCE team has created the dedicated webpage <https://waterforce.eu/workshops/shallow-water> (see Figure 2-13) with the workshop description and agenda.

Figure 2-13: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Shallow water and floating matter remote sensing"

2.1.6 Citizen Science for the CAL/VAL of satellite aquatic products

This online workshop, that took place the **11th of October of 2022** from 13:00h to 15:30h CEST, aimed at exploring the possibilities of Citizen Science for calibration and validation of Copernicus water quality and quantity products.

Regarding the dissemination, the Water-ForCE team has created the dedicated webpage <https://waterforce.eu/workshops/citizen-science> (see Figure 2-14) with the workshop description and programme.

Additionally, an outcomes report was published:

<https://zenodo.org/record/7361601#.Y4oo93bMK3B>

Figure 2-14: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Citizen Science for the CAL/VAL of satellite aquatic products".

2.1.7 Water Quality Continuum Atmospheric Correction Workshop

Given the importance of atmospheric correction and adjacency effect correction processing steps for deriving water-leaving reflectance and higher-level water quality products, this workshop had three main objectives. Firstly, to present ongoing R&D project results on i) atmospheric correction for inland and coastal waters and ii) atmospheric correction validation with in-situ data for inland and coastal waters. Secondly, to provide recommendations (incl. additional spectral bands) for atmospheric correction and validation for future Copernicus water quality products. And finally, to prioritize recommendations.

In terms of dissemination, the Water-ForCE team has created the dedicated webpage <https://waterforce.eu/workshops/water-quality-atm> (see Figure 2-15) with the workshop description and programme.

Figure 2-15: Webpage dedicated to the workshop entitled "Water Quality Continuum Atmospheric Correction Workshop".

2.2 Webinar materials

2.2.1 Water and agriculture

Within the webinar 'Water and agriculture', which was held on January 26th, 2022 three speakers were invited to give their views on water quality and quantity issues (from water run-off from agriculture or pollution of surface water for irrigation to drought, extreme rainfall and soil moisture) regarding the water and agriculture goals for the Copernicus Roadmap.

In terms of dissemination, a webpage for the webinar was created <https://waterforce.eu/webinars/water-and-agriculture> (see Figure 2-16), which includes a brief presentation of the webinar, and a link to the videos of the three speakers' presentations.

Figure 2-16: WaterForCE webpage of the “Water and Agriculture” webinar.

2.2.2 WSDG6 clean water and sanitation

The ‘WSD6 clean water and sanitation’ webinar, held on February 23rd, 2022 the targets of the Sustainable Development Goal number 6 (SDG6) on clean water and sanitation were discussed, with the participation of three guest speakers.

In terms of dissemination, a webpage was created (<https://waterforce.eu/webinars/sdg6-clean-water-and-sanitation>) (See Figure 2-17), which includes a brief explanation of the webinar, the videos of the speakers’ presentations and the documents that were displayed.

Figure 2-17: WaterForCE webpage of the “SDG6 clean water and sanitation” webinar.

2.2.3 Copernicus for Africa

In the ‘Copernicus for Africa’ webinar held on March 30th, 2022 the results and possibilities from the Copernicus aquatic applications to collaborate with African projects were discussed, with the help of three guest speakers.

In terms of dissemination, a webpage was created (<https://waterforce.eu/webinars/copernicus-africa>) (See Figure 2-18), which includes a brief explanation of the webinar, the videos of the speakers’ presentations and the documents that were displayed.

Figure 2-18: WaterForCE webpage of the “Copernicus for Africa” webinar.

2.2.4 Public-Private partnerships for Copernicus water services

Water-ForCE is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020-research and innovation programme under grant agreement number: 101004186.

The ‘Public-Private partnerships for Copernicus water services’ webinar, held on April 27th, 2022 analyzed how European and international regulations enable Copernicus water applications. The webinar also addressed the impact of policies of commercial activity in the water sector regarding the Copernicus programme.

In terms of dissemination, a webpage was created (<https://waterforce.eu/webinars/public-private>) (See Figure 2-19), which includes a brief explanation of the webinar, and some of the videos of the speakers’ presentations and the documents that were displayed.

Figure 2-19: WaterForCE webpage of the “Public-Private partnerships for Copernicus water services” webinar.

2.2.5 EU Funding 4 Copernicus Water Applications

The ‘EU Funding 4 Copernicus Water Applications’ webinar, held on June 1st, 2022 outlined the current funding sources for Copernicus water applications, and some success stories were shared. Two guest speakers were invited.

In terms of dissemination, a webpage was created (<https://waterforce.eu/webinars/eu-funding>) (See Figure 2-20), which includes a brief explanation of the webinar, and some of the videos of the speakers’ presentations and the documents that were displayed.

Figure 2-20: WaterForCE webpage of the “EU Funding 4 Copernicus Water Applications” webinar.

2.2.6 Summer edition: Copernicus 4 Recreational Inland Waters

In the ‘Summer edition: Copernicus 4 Recreational Inland Waters’ webinar, held on June 29th, 2022 the Copernicus tools to monitor the health of inland water bodies to maintain the safety of water activities were discussed. For this purpose, two guest speakers were invited.

In terms of dissemination, a webpage was created (<https://waterforce.eu/webinars/recreational-inland-waters>) (See Figure 2-21), which includes a brief explanation of the webinar, and the videos of the speakers’ presentations and the documents that were displayed.

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Summer edition: Copernicus 4 Recreational Inland Waters

June 29, 2022 16:00 CET | Free registration

With the onset of the summer season, residents and tourists alike spend an increasing amount of time near rivers, lakes, and other bodies of inland water. Hence, it is critical to monitor their health, especially pollution hazards, to maintain the safety of water activities. This can be difficult since many lakes and rivers are huge, some are isolated, and certain locations have so many water bodies that monitoring them insitu can be unattainable. During our sixth webinar, we will discuss the Copernicus tools that allow us to accomplish this task.

Speakers:

- Grega Milcinski CEO and co-founder of Sinergise, specialising in software for advanced geospatial applications, helping Europe to efficiently manage and control agriculture policy and introducing land administration systems to developing countries in Africa. He will present on the topic "Blue Dot Water Observatory - monitoring of water bodies around the world"

[Video >](#)

- Dr. Mark Matthews is the founder and director of CyanoLakes, a company driven to deliver the full benefits of EO data to the water industry and

Figure 2-21: WaterForCE webpage of the 'Summer edition: Copernicus 4 Recreational Inland Waters' webinar.

2.2.7 Technical needs for Copernicus Inland Water Monitoring Service

In the 'Technical needs for Copernicus Inland Water Monitoring Service' webinar, held on October 26th, 2022 the technical aspects of Inland Water Monitoring within the Copernicus Programme were discussed, thanks to the participation of two guest speakers.

In terms of dissemination, a webpage was created (<https://waterforce.eu/webinars/inland>) (See Figure 2-22), which includes a brief explanation of the webinar, and the videos of the speakers' presentations and the documents that were displayed.

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Technical Needs for Copernicus Inland Water Monitoring Service

October 26, 2022 16:00 CET | Free registration

Copernicus data contributes to a better understanding of water quantity and quality. However, water-related products are scattered across the different Copernicus Services. The technologies and expertise needed to exploit this EO data for inland water monitoring can help define a wider Copernicus water service portfolio.

During our seventh webinar, we will be having a discussion on the technical aspects of Inland Water Monitoring with Copernicus.

Speakers:

- Silvy Thant has a background in geography and marine and lacustrine sciences. She is working for the consultancy agency Antea Group Belgium for 8 years and is involved in international Multi Hazard Risk Assessment & Data Driven Solutions (incl. AI techniques) projects as a project leader. Silvy will present "Exploring the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to Optimize the Exploitation of satellite EO and modelling data".

Figure 2-22: WaterForCE webpage of the ‘Technical Needs for Copernicus Inland Water Monitoring Service’ webinar.

2.2.8 Copernicus for Inland Water Biodiversity Monitoring

The ‘Copernicus for Inland Water Biodiversity Monitoring’ webinar, held on November 30th, 29th, 2022 reviewed the ways that the Copernicus services are being used to monitor biodiversity in inland waters, thanks to the participation of two guest speakers.

In terms of dissemination, a webpage was created (<https://waterforce.eu/webinars/inland-biodiversity>) (See Figure 2-23), which includes a brief explanation of the webinar.

Figure 2-23: WaterForCE webpage of the ‘Copernicus for Inland Water Biodiversity Monitoring’ webinar.

3 Summary

To summarize, the Water-ForCE team has created and put in place several materials using different tools that can be used by the project team for any future dissemination or communication event:

- Water-ForCE general presentation in slides format (provided in [Annex A1](#)) including project context, general objectives and expected outcomes.
- Water-ForCE general presentation in poster (A0) format (see Figure 2).
- Stakeholder engagement quiz (provided in [Annex A2](#)) that can be easily modified to suit any event, the quiz is developed using [typeform](#) and is connected to the project CRM [hubspot](#).
- Registration (see Figure 2-10) and Contact forms templates in [hubspot](#) that can be easily modified to suit any event.
- Templates for name tags (see Figure 2-11) and attendees list (see Figure 2-12) for onsite events

This document also puts together the final materials that were used to disseminate and communicate the webinars and workshops.

Annex

A1. Detailed presentation Water scenarios for Copernicus Exploitation

The slide features a dark blue background with a light blue horizontal bar and a brown vertical bar. The title 'Water - ForCE' is in large white font. Below it, 'Water scenarios For Copernicus Exploitation' is written in white, followed by the author's name 'Tiit Kutser' in light blue. A circular inset image shows a cracked, dry landscape. At the bottom right, there is a small European Union flag icon and a line of text: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004186'.

Copernicus Services

All deliver some water or hydrological parameters as services

Shortcomings identified by the EC

- ❖ Better understanding of the whole water cycle needed, but related products are split between different Copernicus Services.
- ❖ Need in more water related products (by which Service?)
- ❖ Optimization of effort (e.g. lake water quality by Land Service, coastal by Marine Service; processing of Sentinel-2 by most Services)

EU Horizon 2020 Space Programme

Copernicus evolution: Mission exploitation concept for WATER

Scope:

The main goal is to analyze current and planned EO space capacities together with innovative processing, modelling and computing techniques to reinforce the existing portfolio offered under Copernicus and to propose an integrated approach for a coherent and consistent inland water monitoring system.

EU Horizon 2020 Space Programme

Copernicus evolution:
Mission exploitation concept for WATER

**Coordination and Support Action
= no research**

Water-ForCE approach

**Develop Roadmap for Copernicus
WATER services**

The Roadmap

- ❖ Analyse EU policies (Water Framework Directive, Bathing Water Directive, Flood Risk Directive, etc.) to identify where Copernicus Services could be more effectively used both in developing policies and monitoring their implementation.
- ❖ Identify gaps and enlarge service portfolio (based on user needs)

The Roadmap

- ❖ Develop higher level biogeochemical products
- ❖ Specify requirements for future Copernicus sensors (e.g. Sentinel-2E new bands) to improve water portfolio
- ❖ Facilitate closer cooperation between *in situ*, remote sensing and modelling communities
- ❖ Propose the design of *in situ* networks so that they can support Copernicus WATER Services better

The Roadmap

- ❖ Define the relationship between Core Services and Downstream Services
- ❖ Recommendation on the evolution of WATER services under the Copernicus programme

Water-ForCE Project: Work Packages

WP 1. Policy, stakeholder, and service analysis

- ❖ Compile the list of stakeholders (individuals, researchers, user organisations, etc.)
- ❖ Assess sectorial policies and legislation
- ❖ Report on user needs and requirements
- ❖ Report on business opportunities
- ❖ Provide directions to WP2-WP5 and input for the Roadmap

WP 2. Water quality continuum

- ❖ Create an international working group (i.e. engage GEO AquaWatch and other relevant organisations)
- ❖ Gap analysis of Copernicus water quality products
- ❖ Develop higher level biogeochemical products
- ❖ Technical needs for future Sentinels

WP 3. Water quantity

- ❖ Create an international working group (remote sensing and water resources experts)
- ❖ Gap analysis of Copernicus hydrological and water balance products
- ❖ Technical needs for future Sentinels
- ❖ Input to the Roadmap from the water quantity and hydrology point of view

WP 4. Aligning *in situ* and satellite Earth observation activities

- ❖ Create an international working group (strengthen links between *in situ* and RS communities)
- ❖ Standard operating procedures for *in situ* networks
- ❖ *In situ* data collection and satellite cal/val recommendations for the Roadmap (what kind of *in situ* networks are needed to support delivery of properly validated RS and modelling products)

WP 5. Modelling and data assimilation

- ❖ Create an international working group
- ❖ Gap analysis (Copernicus needs for modellers and decisionmakers)
- ❖ Recommendations on better integration of RS and modelling for better decision support.
- ❖ Recommendations for the Roadmap

WP 6. Roadmap for the Copernicus WATER services

- ❖ Capacity building requirements and priorities for research and innovation
- ❖ Business innovation and service delivery
- ❖ Compiling the Roadmap
(organising a workshop (mid-2023) where the draft Roadmap will be analysed in a broad international community)

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A2. Quiz prepared for Water Innovation Europe

Water - ForCE

Hello! Do you want to contribute defining the future of inland water services for Copernicus?

Description (optional)

Start press Enter ↵

⌚ Takes X min

1→ **What's your name?**

Description (optional)

Type your answer here...

OK ✓ press Enter ↵

2 → **What's the name of your organisation?**
Description (optional)

Type your answer here...

OK ✓ press Enter ↵

3 → **What type of organisation do you work for?**
Description (optional)

Choose as many as you like

- A Private Sector**
- B Public Sector**
- C SME**
- D Research**
- E NGO**
- F Producer of Earth Observation data/products**
- G Other**

[Add choice](#)

4 → **What water-related information are you using?**

Description (optional)

Choose as many as you like

- A Water quality
- B Water quantity
- C Water supply
- D Sanitation
- E Hydrology
- F Climate
- G Resilience
- H Drought
- I Floods
- J Other

[Add choice](#)

5 → **To what degree do you use Earth Observation data?**

Description (optional)

- A Not at all
- B Occasional user of in situ data
- C Occasional user of remote sensing data (Copernicus or other)
- D Expert user of in situ data
- E Expert user of remote sensing data (Copernicus or other)

[Add choice](#)

6 → Which water-related policies do you deal with?

Description (optional)

Type your answer here...

SHIFT + Enter to make a line break

OK ✓ press Enter ↵

7 → What are the biggest barriers to the uptake of satellite remote sensing in the inland water and coastal domain?

Description (optional)

Choose as many as you like

- A There are no barriers
- B Available data does not provide enough resolution
- C Lack of information about available products and services
- D Lack of training on how to use data
- E Lack of centralised data store
- F Data difficult to download
- G Lack of confidence in data quality and documentation
- H Lack of comparability with traditional in situ monitoring programmes
- I Lack of organisational commitment to invest in EO skills
- J The perception that satellite data cannot be interpreted without extensive processing
- K Other

[Add choice](#)

8 → What are the biggest information needs with regards to satellite remote sensing for coastal and inland water?

Description (optional)

Choose as many as you like

- Need of (Near) Real Time data
- Higher spatial resolution
- Higher temporal resolution
- Longer time series
- Comprehensive water quality indicators
- Water quantity - drought forecasting
- Water quantity - drought monitoring, detecting desertification
- Water quantity - flood forecasting
- Water quantity - flood monitoring
- Water quantity - river flow monitoring
- Water quantity - information on reservoirs
- Water quantity - soil moisture
- Agriculture - detection of soil salinisation
- Agriculture - monitoring of water use
- Agriculture - prediction of areas of reduced food production
- Agriculture - monitoring compliance of buffer zones from waterways
- Water supply - detection of nutrient inflows impacting water quality
- Water supply - detection of leakage from the supply network
- Risks to the water system - overgrowth, subsidence, sedimentation
- Risks to the surrounding area - damage to flood defences, illegal buildings, subsidence
- Geomorphology of rivers and estuaries
- Robust integration with in situ monitoring
- Other

[Add choice](#)

9 → Should data be provided free of charge by Copernicus, or as paid-for products by the private sector?

Description (optional)

- A Free of charge by Copernicus
- B Paid for products by private sector
- C Mainly free of charge but I would not mind to pay for adapted products

[Add choice](#)

10 → **Is there a need for a whole-systems approach which integrates satellite EO water quality and quantity products with land use data to detect unsustainable land use practices?**

Description (optional)

A No need

B Moderate need

C Urgent need

[Add choice](#)

11 → **A last question, just for fun. Where do you think this picture is?**

Description (optional)

A Australia

B Iran

C Finland

[Add choice](#)

12 → The answer is Lapland, the largest and northernmost region of Finland.

Would you like to be informed of our activities and workshops?

We will use your e-mail just for specific communications about the project.

name@example.com

OK ✓ press Enter ↵

